

Iron Age Celtic Spain and Portugal (Celtiberia)

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Entry tags: Syncretic Religions, Religious Group, Pantheistic, Celtic Religions, Indo-European, Language, Polytheistic, Indo-European Religion, Celtic Paganism, Celtic Polytheism

This entry pertains to Celtic language-speaking population groups in the Iberian peninsula, coterminous with modern-day Spain and Portugal. We know about the presence of Celtic tribes in the region from Classical writers, as well as linguistic research which provides us with a rich body of evidence. This consists of inscriptions, dedications, contracts etc., dating to the last three centuries BCE. Additionally, there is evidence from place names, which are particularly helpful in distinguishing between Celtic-speaking peoples and those speaking other languages in and around the region. Archaeological evidence pertaining to settlement, burial, weapons, costumes and pottery also help us distinguish between Celtiberian culture and other Iron Age cultures of Spain and Portugal. Settlement features included both round and rectangular houses, as well as fortified settlements with thick walls. Depending upon region and geography, the economy included herding and a variety of agricultural strategies based on the local environment. There were extensive cremation cemeteries, as well as round graves covered by cairns of stones. Evidence of metallurgy exists in some areas, and grave goods included personal items, ornaments, and weapons of bronze and iron. In terms of religion, in some areas there are votive inscriptions pertaining to local gods, quite a few of which can be readily identified as Celtic deities. These inscriptions provide information about indigenous gods and goddesses who were worshiped on hilltops, near bodies of water, and in relation to other sanctified features of the landscape. Small shrines are found in a number of locations, often with solar or celestial symbols. There is evidence for the veneration of local divinities, as well as some known in other contemporary Celtic regions. Indigenous Celtiberian deities included the goddesses Biogena ("Mother of Cattle"), Drusuna (whose name may signify a connection with the oak tree), Ataecina (possibly associated with night time and/or the underworld), Amma (a mother goddess), and the Duillae (who appear to be a female triad associated with foliage or trees). Male deities included Arco, Vacocius, the Lattuerii (gods possibly associated with war); Teutates (an epithet seen in other Celtic regions, denoting "the god of the tribe"); and the Duiris Ordaecis, whose name may contain the word for "hammer" (depictions of a hammer deity occur elsewhere in the ancient Celtic world, a symbol that may have to do with thunder, or powers of life and death). Deities known to have been venerated in other Celtic cultural contexts included the widely-worshiped god Lugus (known in Gaul and other locations, whose name appears to be cognate with that of the multi-skilled Irish god Lug); Epona (a widely worshiped goddess in the ancient Celtic world, associated with horses, fertility, and journeys to the afterlife or Otherworld); Bormanus (also venerated at thermal springs and sanctuaries in Gaul); and Nemedus (whose name contains the root word "nemed / nemet" meaning "sacred place", variants of which occur in other Celtic regions). One of the most unique features of Celtiberian artwork pertaining to the physical expression of religious ideology are large granite sculptures in the shape of boars and bulls, known as "verracos". These appear to have played an important role in the religion of the pre-Roman population. Representations of human heads, a symbol found widely throughout the Celtic-speaking Iron Age world is one of many important symbols connecting these cultures with others on the Continent and in Ireland and Britain. These also include representations of birds, animals, and fish; plant motifs; solar and lunar motifs; and triplism pertaining to deities or religious symbols. Life-size stone figures armed with round shields and daggers are found near some fortified settlements. Referred to as "guerreros galaicos", they are often depicted wearing neck rings known as torques. These ornaments have been found in the archaeological record, consisting of heavy gold penannular rings with various types of decoration on their terminals, including horsemen; solar barques; animals, birds and other important religious symbols and ideological elements.

Date Range: 600 BCE - 300 CE

Region: Iron Age Spain and Portugal / Iron Age Celtiberia

Region tags: Europe, Spain, Portugal

Iron Age Spain and Portugal prior to full Romanization in the early centuries of the Current

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Curchin, Leonard, 'The Romanization of Central Spain', (London / New York: Routledge, 2004)

– Source 2: Arenas-Estaban, J. Alberto, ed., 'Celtic Religion across Space and Time', (Toledo: Junta de Comunidades de Castilla-La Mancha, 2010)

– Source 3: Full bibliography listed in notes below:

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Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: Celtiberian Ideologies and Religion - UWM Digital Commons
<https://dc.uwm.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1024&context=ekeltoi>
- Source 1 Description: Academic article about Celtiberian Ideologies and Religion from the digital journal E-Keltoi
- Source 2 URL: <https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:495111e9-ad8e-469a-a123-ec91209d8595/files/maca90192b678df727725ee8aed857ace>
- Source 2 Description: Oxford University thesis on the evidence of images and monuments for cultural identity in Roman Celtiberia
- Source 3 URL: <https://dc.uwm.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1029&context=ekeltoi>
- Source 3 Description: Academic article about Celtic Gods of the Iberian Peninsula

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/journal-of-roman-archaeology/article/novallas-bronze-tablet-an-inscription-in-the-celtiberian-language-and-the-latin-alphabet-from-spain/780074C0BFB10B6ADA1D308E30344449>
- Source 1 Description: Academic article about the inscribed Novallas bronze tablet
- Source 2 URL:
https://www.academia.edu/en/362362/Religion_language_and_identity_in_Hispania_Celtiberian_and_Lusitanian_rock_in:
- Source 2 Description: Academic article on religion, language and identity in Celtiberia
- Source 3 URL:
<https://oxfordre.com/classics/classics/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780199381135.001.0001/acrefore-9780199381135-e-6027?p=emailAQe7mdeyKPPJM&d=/10.1093/acrefore/9780199381135.001.0001/acrefore-9780199381135-e-6027>
- Source 3 Description: Pre-Roman scripts and languages in ancient Spain and Portugal

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: In many parts of the region there was fierce resistance to the arrival of the Romans.

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In some (but not all) regions, inscriptions contain information pertaining to social structure in that the group identity of an individual was defined by worship of a particular tutelary god. Lenerz-de Wilde (in Green 1996), p. 534 (referencing Untermann 1985)

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: It is unknown if religious officials were supported, especially in earlier times, through the provision of a habitation, food, supplies, livestock, and material goods of some substance. If they were paid with money, this would have happened later in the era, particularly in connection with larger fortified settlements who minted coins.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Field doesn't know

– Yes

Notes: While classical accounts make no mention of pagan priests or priestesses in Celtic Spain, there undoubtedly must have been some sort of religious specialists, who may have corresponded in certain ways to the druids who were reported on in Gaul and Britain. Place names in the region containing the Celtic language word element 'nemet-' refer to a sacred place or sanctuary; in some classical accounts mention is made of the term 'nemeton' ("sacred place") which was sometimes said to refer to a sacred grove in which druids held ceremonies. There is some artwork that could depict priestly figures. A bronze statuette from Paredes de Nava, now lost, showed a possible priest wearing a tall headdress and playing a flute; a terracotta figure from Termes depicted a priest holding a box. A bronze figurine from Toriaso depicts a male figure holding an offering bowl; he wears a cape with a conical hood. The strongest candidate consists of a 1st c. CE bronze figurine from Segobriga, representing a priestly figure with a covered head who holds a plate in his right hand and a staff or scroll in his left. A possible priest with a tall, pointed headdress and standing next to an altar is depicted on a painted vase from Numantia. Also from that region is a painting on ceramic of a powerful looking figure wearing a very elaborate tunic. The head appears to be that of a bird, possibly a raptor, and there is a pointed headdress or triangular symbol on top of its head. It is unclear if this is a priest wearing a bird mask, or a deity. After the arrival of the Romans, there is evidence of Roman style priests and organized religious cults. Curchin 2011: 181-183; Rankin 1996: 263, 280.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

- ↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:
 - No
- ↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:
 - No
- ↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)
 - Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

- No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

- Field doesn't know

Notes: In central Spain, archaeological research shows late Bronze and early Iron Age settlements with longhouses and a population estimated in the several hundreds. Many scholars consider the early Iron Age as a time of continuous agricultural expansion, with an increase in metal production (including the wide availability of iron.) However the climate became wet and rainy in the northern half of the region which seems to have resulted in the abandonment of a significant portion of traditional Bronze Age settlements. In general it appears that early Iron Age settlements developed independently, including phases of settlement and abandonment. It is not clear why some sites were more successful than others and had a longer life. Around the 4th century BCE social structure appears to have become more complex. It seems likely that most of the population lived in dispersed and self-sufficient villages. These consisted of hamlets with five or six houses, and villages with a maximum of 20 to 25 families. This seems to have been the most abundant type of site, found across a good part of the rural area. It is believed that there was not a strong regional political power, and fortified settlements developed alongside open settlements. Later we start to see more evidence for urbanism in certain areas. Large 'castros' or hillforts, as well as open settlements in the early Iron Age of the Spanish meseta, probably had 400 or 500 inhabitants. This represents the upper limit for a purely agricultural settlement. Álvarez-Sanchis and Ruiz-Zapatero in Fernández-Götz, et al., 2014: 204-210. The population of Celtic Spain and Portugal would have varied in different regions and time periods, affected by geography, topography and climate, as well as social conditions and organization. A look at three different tribal groups can inform us about population variation in time and space. Around 220 BCE, only a small part of the tribe known as the Vettones lived in large fortified centers, the largest of which probably had populations of between 800 and 1,500 people. They were home to families who just four or five generations previously had lived in small villages on the same sites. During the late Iron Age, the Vaccaei in the Duero valley lived in large, well-planned settlements that were distant from each other, with few dependent small villages. This layout began during the 4th century BCE. Defensive walls with large ditches enclosed large, well-populated centers with between 1500 and 5,000 inhabitants. The Carpetanian of the middle Tagus Valley experienced considerable demographic and economic growth between 400 and 200 BCE. There is evidence of increasing social complexity, an increase in Mediterranean imports, and the emergence of new chiefs with unstable powers that had to continuously be defended and negotiated. Fortified settlements emerged, as well as tensions, conflicts and competition. Although they never had a centralized political power and hierarchical social organization comparable to that of their neighbors, they were still the most powerful people in the area. The size of their population is suggested by the fact that in 218 BCE, as Carthaginian troops were marching towards the Pyrenees, there was a mass desertion of 3,000 Carpetani mercenaries recruited by Hannibal. This speaks both to the size of the population and the distinctive personality of this population group. Álvarez-Sanchis and Ruiz-Zapatero in Romankiewicz et al., 2019: 155, 159, 161-162 In 154 BCE a war broke out, declared by the Romans against the Celtiberian city-state of Segeda (Zaragoza). Rome mobilized 30,000 men. Segeda allied with Numantia, recruited 25,000 men, and

with 5,000 horses ambushed and defeated the Romans (who lost 6,000 men) at the battle of the Vulcanalia. Segeda was a state-city of the Celtiberian ethnic group of the Belli. Their coins were minted with its name: Sekeida. It was located within the Iberian Peninsula and its area expanded over 44 hectares, compared with Numantia which had 7.2 hectares. Their settlement became the most important oppidum in the northeastern Iberian Peninsula. Archaeological analysis shows an urban area of about 44 hectares, with the population concentrated in a 17-18 hectare area. There is no information about the number of its inhabitants in the Classical sources, but there is some about Numantia at the time of its siege by Rome. Various classical commentators gave its population as 4000, or as 8,000 in peace time. There have been various attempts to estimate the population of the city. The most successful rates an average of 243 inhabitants per hectare, which would propose a population of nearly 1,800 inhabitants in Numantia. If we apply the same ratio to Segeda, it may have had about 4,000 inhabitants at its peak. A different issue would be the number of people living in the broader territory belonging to the city-states. Burillo-Mozota in Fernández-Götz, 2014: 214-215, 221-222.

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
 - No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: While there is no evidence for written scriptures, in many early Celtic cultures there was a great emphasis on the power of the spoken word. Once writing had been introduced, we can perceive an extensive and nuanced system of thought and belief.

- ↳ Are they written:
 - No

- ↳ Are they oral:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are the scriptures alterable:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:
 - No

- ↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:
 - No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

- ↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - Percentage: 10

- ↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
 - Height, meters: 2.5
- ↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
 - Height, square meters: 1.5
- ↳ Height of average monument, meters:
 - Height, meters: 2.5
- ↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - Percentage of area: 15

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

- ↳ Tombs:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Earlier in the target era, we see the widespread use of cremation cemeteries, associated with pottery urns. Later, in some regions, tombs were set up under stone tumuli.
- ↳ Cemeteries:
 - Yes
 - Yes
 - Notes: These were predominantly cremation cemeteries
- ↳ Temples:
 - Yes
 - Notes: In the early part of the era, people lived in small settlements and any type of religious structure would likely have been small, made of wood, stone or turf. The size and sophistication of these would have altered and likely increased as settlement grew, especially in the large fortified settlements. There is some evidence for ritual activity taking place in the eastern portion of settlements, which aligns with other Indo-European cultures, with a focus on sunwise movement in cultural and religious settings.
- ↳ Altars:
 - Yes
 - Notes: There is some evidence for the use of plain stone altars in the early part of the target era. Some were carved with solar symbols and other cultural or religious emblems, typically fairly simple in design. As settlements grew, and as a result of cultural contact with the Romans and other Mediterranean peoples who had systems of writing, there was some adoption of other writing systems, used to create inscriptions and dedications to various deities.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: In some of the larger settlements there is archaeological evidence for ritual activity taking place in the eastern portions of those settlements. There were also cremation cemeteries marked by the presence of stone stelae. The remains of votive offerings have also been found in natural locales, such as mountain tops and near or in bodies of water.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: The many votive inscriptions provide us with evidence for the worship of indigenous deities, some of whom were worshipped on hilltops. These included Lucubo, Lugoves, Teutates ("the God of the Tribe"), Bormanus (associated with thermal-springs) and Adaegina, a goddess who may have been perceived as a goddess associated with night. There is also a potsherd inscribed with what may be a horned or antlered deity, an archetype found in other Celtic regions. Lenerz-de Wilde (in Green 1996), pp. 544-545, 547.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: In some regions "verracos" are present, large granite sculptures of bulls or boars, which are believed to have been considered important in religion. In what is now Portugal, life-sized stone statues referred to as "guerreros galaicos) are found. These frequently are depicted wearing torques and are often present near the entrance areas of fortified habitations or settlements. They could represent heroic figures, ancestors, or protecting deities. Also present are stone pillars with carved images of severed heads, a practice found in other Celtic regions as well as early Irish literature. Lenerz-de Wilde (in Green 1996), pp. 537, 545, 547-548.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Solar and celestial symbols, plants, animals and birds.

– Yes

Notes: Many animals appear to have been sacred to the Celts in various regions, sometimes as a symbol or attribute of a particular deity, or for the animals' own attributes and symbolic or physical powers. Fantastic beasts were sometimes portrayed on pottery and belt buckles, suggesting that animals may have played a role in mythology as well as religion. Bulls and horses appear on coins, and there were terracotta and bronze statuettes of standing or recumbent bulls in both pre-Roman and Roman times. Two bronze bulls heads may have been used as amulets to promote fertility. A bronze bull from Palencia province with a hollow socket at the base enabled it to be fitted onto a pole; this may have been a standard used in religious ceremonies. Horses were prized for their speed and intelligent, and their important in warfare and the economy. Terracotta or bronze models of horses or horses heads have been found in several locations, and there were also bronze fibulas in the shape of a horse, sometimes with a human rider. Bronze figurines of boars, rams, goats and sheep may also have had religious significance. The boar was revered for its ferocity and tenacity, and sheep and goats for fertility. There were large stone sculptures of bulls and boars called 'verracos' which were sometimes located at the entrance to fortified settlements or near cemeteries. Wolf symbolism is also present. There is a written account of a Celtiberian herald whose mantle of office was the wolf skin, and there are depictions on vases from Numantia of humans wearing what appear to be wolf skins. Curchin 2011: 173-175, 191. Animals figure prominently in Celtiberian metalworking. In addition to bronze fibula

shaped like horses, some with a human rider or associated with a human head, there is also a remarkable iron helmet crowned with a bronze bird of prey with movable wings. Composite human and animal figures are depicted on pottery, and animals and birds (complete, in part, or just the head) appear on fibula, pottery, and silver neck rings. Almagro-Gorbea in Moscati 1997: 402-404, 407, 410-411, 413-415, 418-419. Animal symbolism may also have been involved with perceptions about native cosmology. Bronze fibula and the tops of bronze ceremonial staffs sometimes took the form of two horses back to back, facing outwards on each side, with or without a horseman between them. They were decorated with concentric circles along the body of the horses. Because Celtiberian artwork contains crescent symbols which are interpreted as the moon, and circles with radiating lines around them interpreted as the sun, concentric circles may be symbols of the sun, the full moon, or stars. Horses are associated with the sun in several Indo-European contexts. Sometimes one of the horses was decorated with concentric circles surrounded by radiating lines, as well the ancient (and non-derogatory) solar symbol of the swastika denoting movement to the right. On the other horse was a set of concentric circles with a swastika going in the other direction. These objects have been interpreted as possibly representing the sun moving in one direction during the day, and then moving in the opposite direction throughout the night, eventually reappearing at dawn to continue with its right-hand wise (i.e. sunwise) movement. Burillo-Cuadrado and Burillo-Mozota in Haeussler 2017: 257, 262, 258-259, 263-264, 267-268.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- At home
- Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

- Yes

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

- Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

- Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

- Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

- Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

- Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:
– Field doesn't know

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
– Yes

↳ Humans:
– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:
– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:
"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...
– Yes

— Yes

Notes: Throughout the Celtic world we find place-names containing or referring to the word "nemeton", meaning a sacred place or sanctuary, sometimes a sacred grove. These sites included mountain tops, springs, fields, stones, bodies of water, or forest clearings. Classical accounts refer to a sacred oak grove in Burrado; mountains that were venerated in several regions; as well as lakes and cave sanctuaries. Sanctuaries were often located on mountains or in caves. One of the most famous is the open-air sanctuary of Peñalga de Villastar, which contained an inscription to Lugus and had cylindrical rock-cut holes suggestive of offerings, sacrifices or libations. Several pre-Roman cave sanctuaries have been identified in Segovia province, and near Pedraza, Sepúlveda, and Santo Domingo de Silus. The possible remains of small wooden, stone or clay-walled religious buildings or temples may be visible beneath the ruins of Roman temples or buildings. As noted in regards to deities, the names and epithets of gods and goddesses are known from inscriptions from various periods in pre-Roman and Roman eras. Small altars, which may or may not have been inspired by Roman exemplars, contain native symbolism, including sun, moon and stars (represented by right-turning swastikas, crescent shapes, and spoked wheels), as well as conifers, and images of small boats which may represent a voyage to the other world or the afterlife. Some altars were uninscribed in terms of the carving of names (whether deities or worshipers), perhaps because persons or communities, especially in more rural areas, did not have access to or money for literate stonecutters. Another possibility is that users did not want or could not read an inscription, or that the altar was dedicated to a deity whose name was taboo. Curchin 2011: 169, 176-177, 183-186, 191-192. Buildings with specific political purposes or an ideological/religious focus are not very common, and seem to be mostly late Iron Age features. However the ancient sanctuary of Termes, like 'oppida' in many parts of the Celtic world, may have incorporated symbolic and/or ideological aspects, perhaps dedicated to a local founding hero figure or god(s). Alvarez-Sanchis and Ruiz-Zapatero in Fernández-Götz et al., 2014: 210-211 One interesting feature of the Celtiberian oppidum of Segeda has been suggested for a feature in area 5 of the site. Here a large building of 312 square meters was discovered, made up of two walls built of large gypsum blocks that joined at a 120° angle. The structure is isolated and located in a prominent topographic area. Several scholars believe that the smaller easternmost side of the structure has a north-south orientation and that construction was carried out to purposely achieve several orientations from the cornerstone. The bisector of the angle of the cornerstone of 120° aligned with the summit of a hill, as well as the solar sunset at summer solstice. A 90° angle in the cornerstone is oriented towards another prominent hill, as well as sunset at the spring and autumnal equinoxes. The longest side of the structure has an astronomic azimuth direction of 58°, which coincides with the rising of the full moon at the winter solstice, an astronomical event which repeats every 19 years. These scholars believe the monument was built to facilitate the performance of rituals, as its isolated location outside of the city could allow for large numbers of people to gather in its surroundings, as it appears to be an open sanctuary without a roof. Burillo-Mozota in Fernández-Götz et al., 2014: 217-221. In many places fortified enclosures were probably used as pastures and to keep cattle, and public buildings were rare. One exception is Ulaca which had a shrine and an initiatory sauna. This unusual settlement was surrounded by defensive stone walls and may have been controlled by a collective order maintained by strong political and religious power. It has been suggested that seasonal gatherings were held at the site, which may account for the presence of the famous large stone carvings of bulls and boars, known as 'verracos,' found at other sites as well. Alvarez-Sanchis and Ruiz-Zapatero in Romankiewicz et al., 2019: 156, 162. Another interesting site was discovered in the area known as La Dehesa in the upper valley of the Tajo, within a mountainous region classical authors referred to as 'Idoubeda'. It is a large plateau surrounded by limestone cliffs, and rainfall produces a system of mighty springs around the slopes. The original pasture land has never been plowed and has developed a dense oak wood. In the Iron Age it lacked defensive structures but did include monumental architecture with possible symbolic intentions. It is known that in the medieval era there were three very old oak trees that were used for (a) a meeting point, and place to solve disputes or formalize deals; (b) a point of distribution of economic benefits, and (c) for religious purposes (at this stage, Christian in nature). While the trees themselves are not old enough to connect directly to pre-Christian vegetation cults, it is well-known that tree symbolism and veneration appear to have been quite widespread in the ancient Celtic world, whether in relation to ancient or special trees, or sacred groves. Injunctions from the Medieval era prohibiting the veneration of trees and other elements of the natural world demonstrate that at least some of these beliefs, in certain areas, continued to varying degrees. Arenas Esteban in Haeussler and King, 2007: 189-199.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - Optional (common)

– Yes

Notes: There is quite a bit of evidence for religious observances and offerings taking place on mountain tops and hills, which would very likely have entailed a sense of pilgrimage up to the holy site.

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - Obligatory for some

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:
 - Yes
- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other spirit-body relationship:
 - No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:
 - Yes
- Notes: Use of celestial symbolism engraved on altars.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:
– Yes
Notes: Widespread use of cave sanctuaries

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:
– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:
– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):
– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):
– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):
– Yes

Notes: In a number of Celtic cultures, the concept of fate seems to have played fairly significant role in terms of life events, including those that result in a person's demise. Additionally, there was a pronounced focus on wisdom, skill, honor, bravery and other attributes that could result in a person's fame or reputation continuing on after their physical death.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:
– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:
– Yes

– Yes

Notes: There are extensive cremation cemeteries, some marked by standing stones, others consisting of round cairns of stones, or partly covered by round or oval stone structures.

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Yes

Notes: There are two Classical references (Silius Italicus, *Punica* II.3; Aelian, *De Ore Natura Animalium* X.22) which state that among the Vaccaei and the Celtiberians it was a custom to leave their battle dead to be eaten by birds of prey. Lenerz-de Wilde (in Green 1996), p. 535.

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: It is highly likely that the battle dead who were left out so that their flesh could be eaten by vultures, ensuring a prompt and successful journey to the afterlife or other world, may well have been involved in a secondary burial of their bones.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: While some cremation burials contained no grave goods, others contained personal items, weapons (daggers, shields, spears and swords), fibula, belt hooks, arm bands, earrings, decorated sword sheaths, metal ornaments, and torques (neck rings). Some of these items were placed in or beside cremation urns. There were some rich graves that included horse harnesses, fire-dogs, roasting spits and large cauldrons; these may have been associated with clan leaders. Lenerz-de Wilde (in Green 1996), pp. 535-544, 549.

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Field doesn't know

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Elaborate silver neck rings and cups, gold torques, sophisticated bronze fibulae.

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Weapons, painted pottery

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Cemeteries containing cremation burials in or near ceramic urns was very common . While there was a certain amount of homogeneity in tombs in other areas, most people were buried with poor grave goods. However there are some tombs containing weapons, mostly spears and iron knives. In other cemeteries grave goods included personal ornaments such as fibulae, belt broaches, bracelets and necklaces. Álvarez-Sanchis and Ruiz-Zapatero in Fernández-Götz et al., 2014: 206-209. Outside of settlements were cemeteries with stone tumuli, stelae, as well as cremation tombs. The iron weapons found within these reflect variation which may point to differentiated social groups. However most tombs contain very few objects or none at all, and only a few contain many objects. Those with rich grave goods included weapons and fine bronze jewelry. The erection of tumuli visible in the landscape may suggest that some of the dead had been important ancestors who needed to be remembered by future generations. In some regions cemeteries are easy to recognize from the stone stelae that mark cremation tombs. The material culture associated with them represents aristocratic values such as war, hunting, and vessels for the consumption of alcoholic drinks. Álvarez-Sanchis and Ruiz-Zapatero in Romankiewicz et al., 2019: 159, 161. Early on the primary burial rite was cremation in urns. However there is quite a bit of local variation, possibly due to ethnic, chronological and perhaps social differences. Other variants included the appearance of tumuli in pastoral environments, and rows of urns marked with stelae in certain cemeteries. Material assemblages in these cemeteries sometimes appears to reflect a hierarchical social situation. In addition to short swords, spears and round shields, there were handmade urns and painted pottery, along with offering bowls which originated in the last phase of the local Late Bronze Age. There is also quite remarkable variation and sophistication in regards to bronze Fibulae, their shape, style and ornamentation. AlmagroGorbea in Moscati et al, 1999: 400-402.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence for the burial of very young children in tombs under the floors of houses. These could have been children who did not survive birth or early infancy, and who the family wanted to keep close by. Another possibility is that they had a spiritual or symbolic function, perhaps fertility or renewal, or some connection with a family lineage. Álvarez-Sanchis and Ruiz-Zapatero in Fernández-Götz et al., 2014: 207.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is insufficient written evidence to determine whether this belief exists or not.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While we have evidence pertaining to names and attributes of deities, we don't possess ethnographic evidence or native writings that would enable us to know how people perceived, conceived of, or understood the intentions, emotions, knowledge range, and perceptions of their deities.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: However, based on evidence we have from archeology, classical accounts, and native writings from a wide range of ancient Celtic cultures, while we do not possess much in the way of recorded or written myths from these specific Celtic cultures, due to other shared similarities in culture and aspects of religion, we can cautiously extrapolate some useful knowledge about their beliefs and perceptions pertaining to divinities, as responded to in the section above.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– Field doesn't know

– Yes

Notes: The Celts of Iron Age Spain and Portugal were polytheists, but we lack information that would point to any specific type of organization, which seems to be the case throughout much of the ancient Celtic world. Some deities were localized, while others such as Lugus and Epona are known to have been quite widely venerated in other Celtic regions. Evidence pertaining to deities comes from native inscriptions, artwork and Classical reports. Inscriptions: An inscription to Lugus was found on a mountain sanctuary along with the image of what appears to be a figure of a running raven; elsewhere there are images also believed to represent this deity. An inscribed altar dedicated to the Lugoves (Lugus in a pluralistic form, something that occurs with other Celtic deities elsewhere) occurs in connection with a shoemakers association. Other deities included the goddesses Boiogena ("Genetrix of cattle"), Drusuna (possibly linked with the oak tree), Amma (who could be a mother goddess figure), and Duillis (possibly connected with plants or foliage). Male deities included the Lattuerii (possible war gods) and the Duiris Ordaecis (potential connection with the oak tree as well as the hammer, the latter being an attribute of deities also known from other regions, possibly symbolizing war, or life /death, sometimes associated with healing springs). There is also Nimmedus (whose name may be related to Celtic "nemeton", referring to a sacred grove, sacred place or sanctuary). Other deities known through inscriptions, sometimes without accompanying artwork to assist with attributes or gender, include Aius, Arco, Mentoviacus, and Vacocius. Later there is evidence for the veneration of both indigenous and Roman deities, sometimes separately and sometimes paired together based on perceived similarities. Classical accounts: Strabo (3.4.16) claims that the Celtiberians worshipped a god, who is not named, at night during the full moon. Artwork: A vase painting depicts creatures eating fish, as well as a female figure who may be a goddess. On a sculpted frieze is a round bearded male head with small pointed ears and arching branches protruding from the top of his head. A rock carving depicts a figure with human feet, dressed in a tunic, with twin animal heads. A painted vase shows an elaborate doorway decorated with possible solar and lunar symbols; standing in the doorway is a being with human feet, dressed in a tunic, with two heads, each of which only has one eye. A plant that appears to be a tall evergreen tree is growing out of the top of the figure's head. Curchin 2011, pp. 169-172, 175-177, 183, 191. Linguistic and comparative evidence points to other goddess

names: Iccuna (a healing goddess), Abiona / Aibona, Perketunas ("oak" goddesses), Trebaruna, Navia / Nabia (associated with water), Duitera / Dubitera ("dark/er one", possibly associated with night), Rixamae / *Rigisamai (plural form with element meaning "queen" or "royal"), Damona ("divine cow," also venerated elsewhere), Carvonia ("divine deer"), and Crougia (associated with a word for stone). Male gods included: Belenos (venerated in a variety of other Celtic regions), Drusunos (possibly "son of oak"), Equoisos (associated with horses), Loukteros / Louteros (woodworking god), Senaicos (likely containing a word meaning old or ancient), Tongos (god of oaths), Tongos Nabiagos (depicted by a man's head which has iconographic parallels with a deity associated with the river Seine), Endovelecos ("he who sees inside / in the deep"), Airu ("lordly"), Vlatos. Other divinities included: Bandus / Bandua (possibly associated with the tribe, or denoting relationships or associations), and Dercetios ("the seeing one"). There is also evidence for pluralized figures possibly associated with epithets denoting the lower world - Endeiterae (earlier *Andoterai / *Andedúbna / *Andoúnnai) - as well as an epithet Useae possibly relating to the upper world. de Bernardo Stempel in Haeussler and King, 2017: 178-183, 185-189, 194-198. In what is now Portugal, theonyms included: Aetio, Albuclainco, Arantio, Asidiae, Bandi Arbariaico, Bandi Vortiaecio, Bormanico, Endoueleco / Endouellico, Ilurbedae, Marandicui, Saisabro, Viriocelesi, and Vordio Talaconio. d'Encarnaçao and Guerra in Arenas-Estaban 2010: 95-100, 103-112.

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Field doesn't know

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Additional gods known to have venerated in Celtic parts of Spain were Netus and Neton. Their names may derive from the same root as a shadowy and little known Irish god associated with war called Néit. Two deities with a connection to water were Endovellius and Ataecina. The latter may have been a goddess of the underworld. Pliny the Elder discussed the inhabitants upper Anas, who were still Celtic in culture and spoke a Celtic language even after the arrival of the Romans. He stated that they maintained their indigenous religion, in which the goddess Turobriga was prominent. Strabo wrote that the Celtiberians worshipped an unnamed deity at the full moon. They performed their devotions with their families in front of the gates of their townships, and held dances that lasted throughout the night. Diodorus Siculus mentioned that the Celtiberians were noted for their hospitality, and that they regarded strangers as being under the protection of the gods. Rankin 1996: 167, 169, 184, 260, 263, 280. A terracotta jug was painted with a mythical animal-headed figure with legs that could be humanoid, but possibly bird's feet. It has slender upraised arms and is wearing an elaborate garment from the upper chest to the upper thighs; it dates from the 2nd-1st c. BCE and could represent a deity. Large stone statues of warriors have been found, some associated with horses, and others standing upright. Some hold a shield in front of them with a dagger at their side, and wear a large torque or neck ring (symbolic of status or divinity). They could represent historical or legendary heroic figures, or deities. Almagro-Gorbea in Moscati 1961: 411, 419.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– No

- ↳ Incest:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: This is evident from comparisons with evidence from other Celtic cultures in various locations and eras..

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The concept of fate played a role in a variety of written sources in other Celtic regions.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Generosity and hospitality were highly valued.

↳ Done randomly:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes

Notes: As noted in sections above, we can tentatively extrapolate similarities in regards to commonalities between the gods as described in other Celtic contexts, in a careful and informed manner.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes

Notes: Other punishments could include loss of status ("face"), reputation or honour; loss of status or class privileges; loss of power, fame, good reputation; loss of good relationship with inhabitants of the other world.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: This could take the form of health, well-being, heightened senses, divine contact.

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: This could include hearing divine music, being allowed to temporarily view or experience the Otherworld, ingestion of foods or liquids, divine visions, love or sex with divine beings

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Being in a balanced, reciprocal, harmonious and respectful relationship with the inhabitants of the other world was a common theme and goal in number Celtic contexts.

– Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Like many, if not nearly all ancient religions, the people of Iron Age Celtic Spain and Portugal were polytheistic, and in Celtic regions we don't always see (or have evidence for) an organizational schema pertaining to the prolific numbers of deities and divine beings that were honored and/or venerated. In artwork we see a focus on the human head, which may reflect the comments of a Classical commentator in regards to other Celtic regions stating that the Celts believed that the head was the seat of the soul. This belief may or may not have directly tied in with the taking of heads in battle. In the artwork we also see the importance not only of deity figures, but depictions of animals and plants, as well as what appears to be veneration of trees, something that appears in other Celtic-speaking Iron Age regions. Similarly, prior to the arrival of the Romans, it was rare for gods to be represented in human form, and written dedications and inscriptions were also rare. Sculptures - even small terracotta figurines - as well as shrines, were also new arrivals with the Roman occupation. It was a native custom to dance at banquets, and a Classical author who mentioned the people offering rustic cakes to Ceres may actually mean that there had already been an annual agricultural festival having to do with a native goddess associated with agriculture. In Numantia a special day was set aside, presumably once each year, on which fathers would give their daughters in marriage in what was considered "the customary manner." If there was more than one suitor, the father might propose a contest. While no literary sources mention Celtiberians having bathhouses or steam baths, Strabo noted the Lusitanians practicing a 'Laconian' practice of taking a steam bath followed by immersion in cold water. This has led to speculation that the Meseta 'laconica' may have been ritual baths associated with the initiation of boys into manhood. The large number of buried ceramic vessels found in the Eravica baths has been interpreted as the remains of a ritual, the exact details of which are not fully understood. There is to date no definitive proof (yet) that the Celtiberians (or Lusitanians) used steam baths for ritual purposes. Other practices that are more well-documented involve making ritual deposits, including votive offerings into bodies of water. Over 3,000 coins were found in the bed of the river Burejo. Elsewhere, offerings included deer antlers, bull's horns, figurines, and the remains of animals sacrificed to ensure success in battle or protect the people from disease. These included birds, boars, sheep, bulls, and martens. There is also potential evidence of human sacrifice, which was relatively common throughout the ancient world. The discovery of bronze ladles and plates for making food offerings and libations were found at numerous sites, as well as stone altars, some of which were not inscribed despite access to the use of Latin epigraphy. Some remained undecorated, while others were carved with native symbols, including solar and lunar symbols, plant imagery, and depictions of animals (who may have been associated with specific gods). Curchin 2011: 170-173, 186-190, 192. Like other Celtic populations, the Celtiberians were noted by Classical authors for their hospitality, as well as their ferocity in war. A number of authors, including Strabo, Valerius Maximus, Silius Italicus, Justin and Livy, described the people as being fearless in the face of death, engaging in single combat, and being gifted with a great curiosity in regards to anything new or unusual. It appears that they also believed the gods looked kindly upon those who were friendly towards strangers. They believed it was a criminal act to abandon their chief when his life was in danger, or to survive him in battle. They considered it a glory to die in battle, and believed that the souls of those killed in battle went directly to the otherworld if vultures consumed their bodies. Artwork pertaining to this belief has been found the number of locations. Also, if they had devoted their lives to the success of a battle, it was regarded as dishonorable to survive in defeat. Rankin 1996: 169.

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence from several other Iron Age Celtic cultures of taboos pertaining to foods and other activities. This may pertain to the group, maybe something that a person is born with or into, or something that is placed upon them by a deity or religious specialist.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence of beautiful jewelry and high quality weapons being purposely bent or destroyed prior to offering them to the gods.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Attending religious assemblies appears to have been considered important and desirable. Classical accounts note that those who had committed certain offenses were banned from religious assemblies and shunned by others in their population group, which was considered the most severe of penalties in other Celtic contexts.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence from numerous Celtic cultures that wisdom, skill, truth, generosity, loyalty, and bravery were widely considered important precepts and values to embody.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

– Yes

Notes: While small or at home which will observances may or may not have been required, or required on a daily basis, archaeological evidence does point to their having taken place, sometimes in certain parts of the house, or at certain times of the year.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This would depend on the size of the community, which could be a small rural village of under 100 people or a large settlement of several thousand.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not applicable

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: This would pertain to either larger settlements, or those regions and cultures who actually have trained religious professionals.

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: It seems extremely likely that at least during the Iron Age and at larger settlements, that highly trained religious professionals would not only undertake important religious ceremonies, but would also train others and be aware of how trainees or members of the community were performing time tested ritual activities.

Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: This would likely only be practical in small community events, or in regards to religious professionals, trainees and dedicants, and highly regarded members of society in large settlements.

Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: The consumption of ale or mead seems to have been an important aspect of cultural events, certainly during feasts. It is less certain if participants or officiants utilized psychotropic

plant materials or preparations, although like all traditional cultures, they would have been aware of the properties of various plants that grew in their environment. There have been a few academic publications noting the remains of herbs in cups or vessels found in graves, as well as in connection with visionary practices

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are classical accounts stating that at least some of the Celts in the south of Britain and/or what is now Scotland, ornamented themselves with tattoos and/or with designs created with woad (although the exact preparation of the latter is uncertain, even having been experimented with by some academics). There are a few hints that one or both of these may have also taken place in early Ireland. While we don't have direct written accounts concerning Iron Age Celtic Spain and Portugal, some of the religious or supernatural figures painted on pottery vessels, plates, cups, vases and jugs include some very elaborate designs on the bodies and limbs of either human, or part human and part animal beings (which could be supernatural figures, or could represent religious officiants wearing masks and elaborate costumes).

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Uncertain but highly likely

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: After the arrival of the Romans, depending on a person's social class and or profession, some may have had access to formalized education in the Roman style.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: They're just not appear to have been formal bureaucratic organization at the small to mid-sized community levels, and while it is more likely to have existed in some form in the larger settlements, we don't have documentation of how that may have been organized.

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: While there was initially fierce resistance to the arrival of the Romans in many places, and some ongoing, over time some natives may have elected to participate in Roman culture, or have lived in a region where at least some level of participation was unavoidable.

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: This would have pertained only to larger settlements.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This would pertain to the Roman era, and most particularly to more urbanized areas

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Similarly, the Romans were well known for creating water works and incorporating those into the parts of colonial provinces where they lived.

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There may well have been circumstances under which the native population may have been subject to taxes after the arrival of the Romans.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Religious officials may have served as judges. A separate judicial class may have existed in the larger fortified settlements and cities.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Roman systems of jurisprudence would eventually have prevailed at least in more urban areas, or in somewhat less rural regions where there may have been perceived as being a need for such.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The institution involved in the institutionalized punishments noted above would certainly have included the Romans.

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: While their legal code may have been different from how we conceive of that in modern times, or even how the Romans may have conceived of that, all cultures have rules and regulations to ensure the survival and well-being of all. It appears this would have been preserved and transmitted orally.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Notes: This would have primarily only been possible in regards to larger population groups or settlements.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In some regions and time periods this may have been an option in regards to the Roman military.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Both activities may have affected or been provided for some members of the colonized area.

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

– No

Notes: We know there was exposure to other writing systems, some of which were utilized or adapted for certain purposes by the inhabitants of these regions. However widespread literacy would likely only have become a feature of society during the Roman era, and only to people of certain social classes.

– No

Notes: While these writing systems were used for religious inscriptions and dedications, some natives chose not to utilize writing on stone altars or other religious objects. The writing systems may have been of some use in non-religious settings call me including commerce, the sending of messages, and tribal administration.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There were other writing systems used by cultures in the region, which were in some cases utilized or adapted for sending a messages, and commerce, and in religious inscriptions.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: They would have had an oral system of time reckoning, particularly as regards the planting of crops and the moving of herds to higher summer pastures. And undoubtedly had other features in their traditional calendar(s) having to do with seasonal concerns, plants and animals, as well as divinities and other aspects of mythology and belief.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: The Celtiberians would undoubtedly had their own indigenous annual round of religious observances. However with the arrival of the Romans, their formal calendar would have affected some regions and population groups to varying degrees, based on contact with Roman urban centers, interest in Roman culture (or lack thereof), and personal decisions to engage in aspects of Roman culture for potential social benefits, including inclusion in politics and bureaucracy.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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